

Blockchain-Based Counterfeit Product Detection

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Abstract — Due to the lack of transparency, supply chain management regularly had problems with service redundancy, ineffective departmental collaboration, and lack of standardization. Nowadays, product counterfeiting is a fairly widespread occurrence, and it can hardly ever be identified by a simple visual inspection. For genuine businesses, counterfeiters present serious problems, but far too many people are unaware of the full extent of the impact that these products have on brands. Numerous strategies have been developed in the past to circumvent the issue of product counterfeiting. The most widely used techniques involve the use of RFID tags, AI, QR code-based systems, etc. However, each of them had a few drawbacks, like the QR code's ability to be copied from a real product and used on a fraudulent one, the fact that artificial intelligence relies on CNN and machine learning, which consume a lot of computer power, and others. The goal of this initiative is to increase phony goods identification using supply chain history tracking. Blockchain technology, which guarantees the identity and tracking of actual products across the supply chain, enables this. Everything is made decentralized and accessible by multiple parties at once via a blockchain-based system. One of its key benefits is that the data is incredibly safe and protected from any vulnerabilities because it cannot be changed without the approval of all parties involved. This paper offers a system for the detection of fake goods that was created utilizing blockchain technology.

Keywords— Blockchain Techniques, Counterfeit Detection, Product Authentication, Quick Response Code

I. INTRODUCTION

Product counterfeiting is the fraudulent sale of one product as another, leading to consumer confusion and possible financial or other damages. According to a report by the Market Research Organization, counterfeiting costs the Indian economy over INR 1 trillion annually, with instances of counterfeit products increasing at an average rate of 20%

between 2018 and 2020. The term "counterfeit goods" refers to a broad range of products, including counterfeit electronics, apparel, cosmetics, and handbags. Beyond its negative effects on the economy, counterfeiting puts consumers at risk. For instance, inferior cosmetics can damage the skin and create rashes and skin disorders, fake electronic components can impair gadget operation and perhaps lead to dangerous circumstances, and inferior footwear and apparel can be uncomfortable. Therefore, it is crucial to solve this issue.

The harm that counterfeiting does to a company's reputation is another consequence. Since a sizable portion of customers don't realize bought fake goods, might hold the original manufacturer responsible if the fake item malfunctions, degrades quickly, or falls short of their expectations. Customers as a result demand restitution from the actual business, such as refunds or replacement goods.

Numerous impacted organizations frequently encounter a difficult scenario where must handle the complaints of disgruntled clients who gripe about the poor quality of a product. Further complicating issues, customer service staff might not be aware that the item in question is actually a fake. Companies are in a challenging situation because want to ensure consumer happiness while minimizing the time and effort expended dealing with subpar copies of their products. Beyond strained client relations, counterfeiters frequently cause distributors, merchants, and other business partners to lose faith in legitimate businesses.

Network transparency, cost management, pre-supply evaluation techniques, and strong supplier relationship management are the most efficient solutions for reducing the deceptive hazards related to counterfeit items in global supply chains. In order to prevent counterfeiting, this paper's main objective is to propose a method that makes use of Blockchain technology. This technology gives suppliers and end users the power to track a product's progress through the supply chain in a highly secure setting.

Our goal is to address the problem of trademark counterfeiting and give customers, merchants, and suppliers the chance to check the integrity and authenticity of the items came into contact with by giving an overview of the proposed system.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. "Blockchain for Supply Chain Traceability and Product Authentication"[1]

This paper explores the application of blockchain technology to establish provenance and traceability in supply chains to combat counterfeit products. It discusses the capabilities of blockchain to create immutable and transparent product records across the supply chain.

B. "Decentralized Blockchain-based System for Anti-Counterfeiting"[2]

This work focuses on developing a decentralized blockchain system to prevent counterfeiting of luxury goods. It highlights designing product identity IDs, blockchain transactions, and end-user mobile apps to scan and verify authenticity throughout the supply chain.

C. "Product Authentication using QR Codes and Blockchain"[3]

This research aims to leverage QR codes and blockchain to authenticate products in supply chains. It examines generating unique QR codes for products, recording identity details on a blockchain, and enabling customers to scan codes and retrieve data to verify authenticity.

D. "AI and Blockchain for Supply Chain Security"[4]

This paper explores integration of artificial intelligence and blockchain for enhancing supply chain security. It discusses using AI to detect anomalies in supply chain data and trigger blockchain transactions to identify potential counterfeits and authentication issues.

E. "Challenges in Blockchain-based Anti-Counterfeiting Systems"[5]

This review identifies key challenges in developing blockchain-based anti-counterfeiting systems including integration complexity, user adoption, and scalability. It provides insights into current limitations that need to be addressed to realize the full benefits of blockchain in this domain

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology describes the implementation details of the blockchain-based supply chain tracking system designed to detect counterfeit products. The decentralized application is

developed on the Ethereum blockchain network to provide transparency and prevent tampering of product records.

A. Platform Selection:

The Ethereum blockchain network was chosen to develop the decentralized application, due to its smart contract functionality and maturity as a blockchain platform. The Solidity programming language was used for writing the smart contracts.

B. System Design:

The system architecture was designed to have three key roles - manufacturer, supplier, and customer. Each party can add product data into the blockchain via transactions through a web application.

C. Smart Contracts:

Two smart contracts were developed - one for manufacturers to add new products, and one for suppliers to update product locations. The contracts contained functions like `addProduct()`, `updateLocation()`, etc. Inheritance was used to separate common functionality.

D. Product Identification:

A unique QR code was generated for each product using the `qrcode` npm package. This served as the product's unique identifier as it moved through the supply chain.

E. Local Blockchain Network:

For development and testing, a local Ethereum network was created using Ganache. Accounts, private keys, and a test ETH balance were provided out-of-the-box.

F. Blockchain Interaction:

The Web3.js library was used to integrate the frontend application with the smart contracts deployed on Ganache via Truffle. It enabled invoking contract functions and signing transactions.

G. Transaction Verification:

The Metamask browser extension acted as the Ethereum wallet. It provided transaction signing and notification whenever a contract function was initiated.

H. Supply Chain History:

Customers can scan the QR code via the web app and retrieve the product's supply chain history to verify authenticity.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

For building the blockchain-based anti-counterfeit detection system, follow these steps:

A. Initialize project

Truffle: Initialize a Truffle project for smart contract development. Install dependencies like Web3.js, Metamask, QR code generator.

B. Smart Contracts

Define product and actor structures using Solidity. Implement core supply chain tracking functions. Deploy contracts on local Ganache blockchain using Truffle.

C. Product Identification

Generate unique QR codes for products using the qrcode library.

Map QR codes to product on blockchain.

D. Frontend Application

Build application pages and flows for each system role. Connect to Metamask wallet for transaction signing. Integrate Web3.js to interact with deployed contracts.

E. Testing

Validate app flows and contract functions using sample test data. Measure performance metrics like transaction overhead. Confirm counterfeit detection by tracing sample product histories.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, presented the development of a blockchain-based system to detect counterfeit products by tracking supply chain provenance. The goal of this system is to empower consumers to verify product authenticity and origin before purchase. It also increases supply chain transparency for manufacturers and suppliers.

The system utilizes blockchain technology to create immutable, decentralized records of product journey through the supply chain. Smart contracts encode the core logic to enable each supply chain actor to add time-stamped data as transactions. Unique QR codes linked to blockchain records provide a cryptographic product identifier.

Implemented this architecture using Ethereum for the blockchain network, Solidity for smart contract programming, and Web3.js to interact with deployed contracts. For the frontend application, ReactJS provided interactive interfaces while Metamask enabled transaction signing.

In conclusion, this blockchain-based anti-counterfeiting system offers an efficient approach to track supply chain history. By scanning QR codes, consumers can retrieve provenance trails and detect fraudulent products that deviate from expected paths. The system enhances confidence in product legitimacy and brand reputation. As future work, the performance and security of this system could be tested at enterprise scale across various industries.

VI. REFERENCES

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